

Modeling Diversion in Pebble Bed Reactors for Safeguards Applications

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the proliferation resistance (PR) of the Pebble Bed Fluoride salt-cooled High temperature Reactor (PB-FHR) using the benchmark gFHR model. The implemented hyper-fidelity simulation method provides pebble-resolved data, allowing for focus on both the intrinsic characteristics of plutonium produced within the fuel and the reactor's system-level response under various diversion scenarios. First, the intrinsic PR of plutonium is quantified as a function of pebble burnup and compared to that of conventional light-water reactors (LWRs) and the HTR-10 (gas-cooled pebble bed reactor). Results show that plutonium bred in the gFHR exhibits a lower PR value compared to LWRs due to the graphite moderation, which promotes the formation of Pu-239 at lower burnups. Conversely, the HTR-10 features a lower PR than the gFHR, where the coolant impacts the neutron spectrum and therefore the plutonium quality. At the system level, potential diversion scenarios are simulated by imposing burnup-based thresholds for early pebble diversion. The results reveal a strong sensitivity of the reactor's equilibrium state to diversion: scenarios that yield significant plutonium production induce measurable changes in reactivity (up to +1700 pcm), easily observable through control rod movement, for instance. Another case study considers a mixed core, partially fueled with fertile pebbles, and highlights similar findings, also characterizing the quality of the obtained fissile material.

Keywords: Pebble bed reactor, proliferation, high-fidelity, safeguard

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of Generation IV reactors has prompted the development of new methods for assessing Proliferation Resistance (PR). This need is especially relevant for reactor concepts involving fuel forms and continuously circulating fuels, which diverge from the traditional assembly design found in pressurized water reactors. Pebble Bed Reactors (PBRs), as one of the novel designs under investigation, rely on graphite moderation and utilize spherical fuel elements with embedded TRISO particles. A unique characteristic of PBRs is their continuous refueling, resulting in a multi-pass fuel behavior. Pebbles are inserted at one end of the core and move through the active region over several weeks before being discharged. Upon discharge, their burnup and mechanical integrity are assessed. Depending on whether they meet an operator-defined burnup threshold, pebbles are either reinserted into the core or permanently removed (discarded).

A potential proliferation concern arises from the possibility of diverting pebbles before they reach their intended final discard burnup without stopping the reactor operation. Previous studies have shown that lower burnup pebbles yield higher-grade plutonium, which reduces proliferation resistance [1].

This concern motivates a deeper investigation of such diversion scenarios and a reconsideration of PR evaluation for PBRs. The inherent complexity and flexibility of PBR operation must be comprehensively evaluated to identify and narrow down proliferation pathways. This line of work is further supported by recent advancements in high-fidelity computational tools capable of simulating PBR behavior. Specifically, the High-Fidelity Python framework (HxF) [2] enables detailed modeling of transport, depletion, and pebble movement, providing in-core and off-core, pebble-resolved data. This level

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of accuracy offers the possibility to simulate diversion scenarios and their effect on the reactor equilibrium.

The primary goal of this study is to investigate a specific PBR concept—the Pebble Bed Fluoride salt-cooled High temperature Reactor (PB-FHR)—using the benchmark gFHR model [3], and to evaluate its behavior under a range of diversion scenarios and the corresponding plutonium quality. First, the intrinsic PR of the plutonium produced at different irradiation stages is quantified and compared to that of a conventional pressurized water reactor and to another gas-cooled PBR concept. In the second part, core-level equilibrium calculations are performed for a series of diversion scenarios. For each scenario, the reactor's steady-state characteristics are analyzed and compared to nominal conditions to evaluate potential signatures of diversion. Finally, the total mass of diverted plutonium is compared against the IAEA-defined significant quantity (SQ) [4], enabling a practical assessment of the proliferation potential and informing safeguard detection strategies tailored for advanced PBR systems.

2. REACTOR MODEL AND SIMULATION TOOLS

The study focuses on a salt-cooled PBR, the gFHR [3], which has a cylindrical core enclosed by a graphite reflector. Notably, pebbles are 2 cm in radius and contain 9022 TRISO particles, each of which encapsulates uranium oxy-carbide fuel.

Unlike the original gFHR model, this study assumes that pebbles are arranged in a Face-Centered Cubic (FCC) lattice. This assumption simplifies both the spatial organization of pebbles and the modeling of their dynamic behavior. Within the HxF framework, pebble movement is simulated via a vertical sequential swapping process, in which fuel compositions are exchanged between pebbles after each burnup step, as outlined in Reference [5].

Monte Carlo simulations are performed using Serpent 2 [6], which offers an explicit detailed model of the reactor core, including the reflector, individual fuel pebbles, and the internal TRISO particle structure. The simulations begin with a completely fresh fuel inventory and proceed iteratively until the system reaches an equilibrium core condition, characterized by a stable neutron multiplication factor. Each transport calculation involves 5×10^7 active neutrons and 5×10^6 inactive neutrons. The associated statistical uncertainties are 1.1 % for pebble-wise neutron flux and 2.8 % for pebble-wise power, while the uncertainty in the multiplication factor is kept below 30 pcm. The simulations utilize the ENDF-B/VIII.0 nuclear data library [7]. Further details on the Monte Carlo model of the gFHR and the equilibrium determination process are available in Reference [5].

3. METHOD

To assess the reactor's proliferation resistance, the isotopic composition of pebbles is evaluated at various stages of irradiation, specifically at the time of their discharge from the core. The baseline simulation assumes nominal operating conditions (equilibrium conditions), under which pebbles are removed once their burnup exceeds 170 MW/kgHM. This threshold corresponds to an average residence time of 522 days, as defined in the gFHR benchmark specification [3]. The resulting discharge burnup distribution is presented in Figure 1, categorized by the number of passes each pebble completes through the core. This data enables the analysis of fuel composition as a function of accumulated passes or burnup, serving as a foundation for determining the relationship between plutonium intrinsic proliferation resistance and burnup. The multi-pass nature of the PBR is observable in Figure 1, with overlapping burnup distributions for pebbles that have completed more than six passes due to the pebble shuffling.

Some pebbles accumulate up to nine passes before being discarded, while some of them require only seven passes. Using the discharged compositions and their corresponding distribution, the average Pu and U mass per pebble is presented in Figure 2, along with the associated standard deviations as a function of the number of accumulated passes.

Figure 1. Distribution of discharged pebble burnup as a function of the number of accumulated passes.

Figure 2. Average Pu and U mass per discharged pebble as a function of pass index, including standard deviation.

From the plutonium mass in each vector, the required diversion rate to accumulate 1 SQ (8 kg of Pu [4]) over a year is estimated. For example, diverting pebbles after a single pass would require removing 300 000 pebbles per year. As an element of comparison, the same number of pebbles is discarded over 21 months for the gFHR under normal operation.

3.1. Proliferation resistance calculation

The pebble diversion rate calculation is completed by the intrinsic PR of the Pu material. To assess the intrinsic proliferation resistance of the diverted material, four technical attributes are calculated following the methodology of Mulyana et al. [1]:

- Heat Load: This represents the total thermal power generated by radioactive decay of the Pu isotopes (including alpha, beta, gamma, and neutron emissions).
- Radiation Dose Rate: Calculated one meter from the surface of an 8 kg Pu sphere, this metric accounts for gamma and neutron radiation.
- Spontaneous Fission Neutron Rate: This refers to the emission of neutrons from spontaneous fission
- Rossi-alpha (Rossi- α): This parameter reflects the neutron kinetics of the material. It quantifies the fissile material's multiplication properties.

Each of these attributes is calculated for a hypothetical 8 kg Pu sphere with compositions after 1 year of cooling from its hypothetical diversion. The sphere composition is extracted from the discharged pebble-wise plutonium vectors, covering the entire range of discharged burnup. The attributes are combined to obtain the intrinsic PR of the Pu material.

3.2. Reactor equilibrium assessment

3.2.1. Early diversion

The final component of this study involves performing core equilibrium calculations for a given diversion scenario. The HxF framework provides the modularity required to simulate non-standard pebble handling strategies by enabling the removal (i.e., diversion) of discharged pebbles based on a user-

defined criterion. To reflect realistic PBR operation and potential proliferation pathways, pebbles are diverted selectively based on their burnup level. Specifically, pebbles with a discharged burnup below a defined threshold are considered candidates for diversion. For all scenarios, the pebble operational discard threshold remains set at 170 MWd/kgHM.

Each diverted pebble is replaced with a fresh fuel pebble, maintaining a constant pebble inventory within the reactor. This diversion logic allows the system to reach a new operational equilibrium for each scenario. Once equilibrium is achieved, key reactor parameters—including the effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}), neutron flux, and the discarded pebble burnup—are evaluated.

By comparing these quantities to those from nominal operation, the impact of diversion on core physics can be assessed. Observable deviations in these parameters provide insight into the detectability of diversion activities, supporting a preliminary safeguards analysis. Additionally, metrics such as the total number of diverted pebbles and the corresponding diverted Pu mass are presented, and the relevance of these scenarios is discussed.

3.2.2. Scenarios involving fertile pebbles

A second proliferation pathway considered involves a dual-pebble core configuration. The reactor operates with both standard UCO fuel pebbles (gFHR reference fuel) and fertile pebbles containing either Th-232 or natural uranium, which can transmute into fissile isotopes (U-233 and Pu-239) under irradiation. Fuel pebble and fertile pebble types share identical geometry and TRISO particle structure, differing only in kernel composition. Reactor operation remains nominal; a burnup threshold is set for the fuel pebbles, while the fertile pebbles are discharged after a single pass and replaced by a new fertile pebble. A new equilibrium state is then established, and the diversion scenarios are discussed.

4. RESULTS

4.1. gFHR fuel intrinsic PR values

The first result is the PR value of the Pu vector under normal operation for pebbles discharged after different numbers of accumulated passes, shown in Figure 3. Moreover, the figure presents the result for another PBR concept, the HTR-10 [8], a gas-cooled 10 MWth PBR built in China in 2000 as a demonstration plant. The simulation method and PR calculation are similar for the HTR-10, the burnup threshold being set to 72 MWd/kgHM to ensure criticality of the core. In Figure 3, the PR is computed for both reactors and represented as a function of the pebble burnup. The PR corresponding to the lowest discharged burnup is also represented. A clear linear trend is observed: PR increases with burnup. This is expected because higher burnup drives the accumulation of even-mass plutonium isotopes that degrade weapons usability, while fissile content reaches an equilibrium, as shown in Figure 2. At low burnup, the PR values are relatively low (0.22 for the HTR-10 and 0.28 for the gFHR), indicating a plutonium vector with a higher fissile fraction and lower handling penalties. As burnup approaches typical discard values, PR rises above 0.3 and even above 0.45 for the gFHR.

For comparable burnup, the gFHR exhibits systematically higher PR (by 0.05-0.06) than the HTR-10. This difference stems from the gFHR's higher initial enrichment and its harder neutron spectrum, which together accelerate transmutation of Pu-239 into heavier Pu isotopes, and also enhance in-core fissioning of fissile plutonium, thus reducing the fissile fraction of the plutonium vector. Indeed, calculated equilibrium conversion ratios are about 0.12 for the HTR-10 and 0.44 for the gFHR. Consequently, for the same discharge burnup (25 MWd/kgHM), the Pu-239 mass fraction in gFHR pebbles is about 88 %, versus 93 % in the HTR-10. Figure 4 shows the isotope mass per pebble as a function of burnup for both reactors. Two practical observations follow: (1) the absolute mass of Pu-239 produced per pebble is similar between the two designs, and (2) pebbles with the same burnup within a single reactor exhibit substantial scatter in both plutonium quantity (and thus isotopic quality) because of heterogeneous ir-

Figure 3. PR values for different burnup and different reactors.

Figure 4. Isotope mass production per pebble

radiation histories and variations in fast fluence. This intra-core diversity—more pronounced in the gFHR than in the HTR-10—could complicate the diversion based on a burnup threshold and outlines the requirement of high-resolution burnup measurement capabilities to obtain the expected plutonium quality.

The overall PBR comparison leads to considering the difference in reactor size and thus, pebble circulation rate, significantly impacting the potential plutonium produced mass between the gFHR and the HTR-10. On average, the pebble handling system of the gFHR process about 3800 fuel pebbles each day, while the HTR-10 processes 60 fuel pebbles. This ratio, rated by thermal power of each reactor, gives a strong advantage to the HTR-10 for proliferation resistance.

Finally, a comparison with the intrinsic plutonium PR study of PWR by Mulyana et al. [9], added to the Figure 3, shows that, for similar burnup levels (25 MWd/kgHM), the PBR exhibits lower intrinsic PR despite being a Generation-IV design. This is mainly due to its graphite moderation and softer neutron spectrum, which favor higher Pu-239 retention. However, intrinsic PR alone does not fully represent proliferation resistance. A complete assessment must include attributes related to transportation, chemical processing, and weaponization, which are significantly less common for TRISO-based fuels than for conventional fuel pins. Moreover, the continuous and multi-pass operation of PBRs naturally drives pebbles to higher burnups (≤ 25 MW/kgHM), reducing the share of really low-exposure fuel that could yield more attractive plutonium. This highlights the need for system-level safeguards analyses beyond intrinsic isotopic metrics.

4.2. Early diversion and effect on reactor equilibrium

As illustrated in Figure 3, the PR of plutonium in gFHR fuel increases with burnup. Leveraging this relationship, a set of diversion scenarios is proposed based on a diversion burnup threshold. Diversion thresholds ranging from 22.5 MWd/kgHM to 27.5 MWd/kgHM are selected for analysis to leverage the highest plutonium quality available. Thresholds above 30 MWd/kgHM lead to excessive removal of pebbles, causing an unsustainable influx of fresh fuel that significantly perturbs the burnup distribution and sharply increases excess reactivity—conditions that are both operationally unrealistic and easily detectable. Conversely, pebbles typically accumulate at least 20 MWd/kgHM during their first pass through the core (see Figure 1), establishing a practical lower bound for early diversion.

The results of the three equilibrium calculations are summarized in Table I. It illustrates the trade-off between detectability and plutonium production. At the lowest threshold (22.5 MWd/kgHM), the diversion has a minimal impact on reactor behavior, with a modest increase in the multiplication factor

Table I. Equilibrium characteristics under different diversion thresholds.

Diverted burnup threshold [MWd/kgHM]	22.5	25	27.5	Reference
Diverted pebble burnup [MWd/kgHM]	22.3±0.2	24.0±0.7	25.3±1.5	/
Discarded pebble burnup [MWd/kgHM]	178.1±4.4	178.1±4.4	178.1±4.4	178.0±4.4
Diverted pebble PR	0.278±2E ⁻⁴	0.280±8E ⁻⁴	0.282±2E ⁻³	/
Equilibrium k_{eff}	1.01174	1.01508	1.02738	1.00966
Neutron flux [n/c ² m/s]	2.34E14	2.27E14	2.26E14	2.34E14
Number of diverted pebbles [pebble/year]	350	28000	131000	0
SQ [SQ/year]	0.01%	8.9%	42.6%	0

($\Delta k_{eff} \simeq +200$ pcm), but it yields an insignificant amount of diverted plutonium compared to the SQ metric. At the highest threshold (27.5 MWd/kgHM), a meaningful quantity of plutonium is diverted (approximately 0.42 SQ/year), but this comes at the cost of a large perturbation in the core's reactivity due to the large replacement of diverted pebbles by fresh fuel pebbles ($\Delta k_{eff} \simeq +1700$ pcm), which would manifest in noticeable changes in control rod insertion depth—estimated around 1 meter based on gFHR simulated control rod worth [10]. The intermediate case (25 MWd/kgHM) leads to a moderate increase in reactivity ($\Delta k_{eff} \simeq +600$ pcm) but still falls short of producing a significant quantity of plutonium and requires more than 11 years to reach one SQ production. These results demonstrate the inherent sensitivity of the core to variations in the fresh fuel insertion rate and highlight the potential for diversion detection through changes in reactor control parameters for a significant Pu diversion rate. The reactor flux and discard pebble burnup do not provide additional information and remain similar over the three cases. In terms of PR attributes, the difference in plutonium quality between the two extreme thresholds is negligible, both in terms of fissile mass content and PR attributes.

Considering these three scenarios, a relevant diversion approach would examine an increase in the discard burnup threshold to compensate for the higher fresh fuel insertion rate and mitigate the reactivity surge. Based on sensitivity calculations for the gFHR, the surge of the k_{eff} in the third column of Table I (+1700 pcm) can be mitigated by changing the fuel discard threshold from 170 MWd/kgHM to 158 MWd/kgHM. However, this strategy results in a change in pebble discard rate, potentially detectable.

Realistic diversion strategies must also consider the engineering constraints of the pebble-handling system. In current designs, discharged pebbles pass through a burnup measurement station that directs them either back to the core (if under-burned) or to a storage cask (if fully depleted) via two separate pipes [11]. Implementing a diversion pathway would therefore require an additional discharge branch, which would be readily observable through monitoring or inspection. A more covert option would involve mixing diverted pebbles with the normally discharged (depleted) ones and subsequently separating them off-site during post-irradiation processing. However, this approach introduces additional challenges, including the handling of larger volumes of material, increased transportation complexity, and new criticality safety constraints for the storage system due to the higher fraction of low-burnup, fissile-rich pebbles compared to the designed inventory. Overall, the studied scenarios involve accurate burnup measurement capabilities.

4.3. Proliferation scenarios involving two pebble types

The observations of the previous section drive the study towards a different approach, featuring the feeding of fertile pebbles. Six equilibrium cases are simulated to assess the impact of introducing fertile

pebbles into the gFHR core. Three fractions of fertile pebbles—10 %, 20 % and 30 % of the total incore inventory—are considered. For each fraction, two distinct fertile materials are tested independently: thorium dioxide (Th-232) and natural uranium (U-nat). The fertile pebbles are replaced after one single pass by a new fertile pebble. The simulations reveal that increasing the fraction of fertile pebbles systematically reduces the equilibrium reactivity and neutron flux due to the reduced fissile loading. In this case, the fuel discard burnup threshold is adjusted to compensate for the reactivity penalty, and the results are presented in Table 4.3, containing the adjusted burnup threshold to discard fuel pebbles, the fissile mass obtained in the fertile pebble (U-233 or Pu-239), and the corresponding produced SQ per year of operation of the gFHR. According to the IAEA, the SQ for Pu and U-233 are 8 kg [4].

Table II. Equilibrium characteristics under different fertile pebble fractions

		Adjusted discard threshold [MWd/kgHM]	Fissile mass per pebble [mg]	SQ [SQ/year]
Thorium	10%	163	62.3	1.09
	20%	158	62.5	2.18
	30%	150	62.4	3.28
U-nat	10%	158	45.2	1.04
	20%	148	45.1	2.08
	30%	136	45.0	3.12

The six simulated cases reveal a clear impact on the reactor’s equilibrium state, requiring a reduction of the fuel discard burnup threshold ranging from -7 to -34 MWd/kgHM, with the largest adjustment observed for cores containing 30 % natural uranium fertile pebbles. The fissile mass produced in the fertile pebbles is lower for Pu-239 than for U-233, mostly related to the higher fission cross section of Pu-239 compared to U-233. In terms of isotopic quality, the plutonium vector after a single pass contains at least 17 wt% Pu-240, while the uranium vector includes approximately 100 ppm U-232—both compositions, which prevent weaponization. The buildup of about 22 mg of Pa-233 per thorium pebble should also be considered for separation, as it could later decay to U-233 and provide pure fissile material.

Finally, additional configurations with smaller fertile fractions (e.g., 5 %) could be explored for their lower detectability, although they would yield negligible SQ. Conversely, higher SQ production leads to pronounced perturbations in the reactor equilibrium and yields plutonium and uranium of poor isotopic quality, even after a single pass. Overall, it is worth emphasizing that such scenarios depend strongly on the system’s ability to identify and distinguish fertile from fuel pebbles—an area requiring further research—and highlight the sensitivity of reactor reactivity control through burnup threshold adjustment as a potential indicator of undeclared breeding activities.

5. CONCLUSION

This work leverages the high-fidelity framework HxF for PBR simulation to provide valuable information for non-proliferation analysis. It involves the calculation of the intrinsic proliferation resistance of the plutonium vector for several discharged burnups of two PBR concepts, and also considers diversion scenarios and their impact on the reactor’s equilibrium state. In summary, the intrinsic PR of plutonium produced in the gFHR increases with burnup, and overall offers a higher intrinsic resistance compared to the HTR-10 but a lower value than traditional PWR for similar burnup. However, intrinsic PR alone is insufficient; a complete assessment must consider full attribute analysis, including fuel form, chemical separability, transportation, and weaponization. Additionally, the above-mentioned detectability of diversion scenarios should be implemented within the overall PR calculation.

The study demonstrates the high sensitivity of the gFHR to diversion strategies, including both early

fuel diversion and the introduction of fertile pebbles. Achieving significant quantities (SQ) of plutonium or uranium—on the order of 1 SQ/year—induces notable perturbations in the reactor's equilibrium, particularly in excess reactivity. These effects could be detected through measurable changes in control rod insertion or shifts in the discard burnup threshold. Although the inherent operational flexibility of PBRs allows for many potential diversion paths, all significant diversion scenarios ultimately disrupt the reactor's steady-state conditions and require a pebble handling system update and strong burnup measurement capabilities. Moving forward, safeguards research should focus on standardizing pebble handling system designs. Therefore, systematic reporting and monitoring of the operator-declared discard burnup threshold could serve as a key safeguard indicator, helping identify deviations linked to potential diversion activities.

Future work could include a more complete PR calculation involving transportation and transformation stage applicable to pebble and TRISO fuel form.

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